

Predicting Chaos in the Three-body Problem with Quaternion-valued Neural Networks

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The main result of the recent Double Asteroid Redirection Test (DART) mission, performed by NASA, consisted in the first evidence of the possibility of diverting the orbit of a celestial body. The mission planning took care of several factors, many of them uncertain, and resulted in a successful attempt which paved the way for future mission aimed at protecting the planet from dangerous collisions with other celestial bodies. The DART mission has been recently discussed in terms of its nonlinear dynamics through simple mathematical models based on the classic Kepler problems, analysed by using appropriate integration algorithms and by means of an analog/digital electronic circuit emulator to realize faster and qualitative more efficient experiments. In this communication, we focus on the special case of the occurrence of chaotic oscillations in the three-body problem, where the high sensitivity on initial conditions and digit precision makes even the analogue approach less practical. The use of quaternion-valued neural networks to predict the behavior in these case is explored showing the possibility of a good prediction of chaos even in presence of a limited precision.

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1. Introduction

The Double Asteroid Redirection Test (DART) mission consisted in launching a spacecraft towards the binary asteroid system composed by Dimorphos orbiting around Didymos. The spacecraft impacted the surface of Dimorphos with a consequent momentum transfer that diverted the asteroid over a different orbit, with a shorter orbital revolution period around Didymos. This spectacular result made the mission as the first successful attempt proving the possibility of diverting the trajectory of asteroids [1, 2].

Recently, the DART mission has been investigated from a nonlinear dynamics point of

view [3]. The mission, in fact, has been modeled by adopting simple nonlinear dynamical systems able to conceptually reproduce the dynamics of the binary asteroid system and the orbital change resulting from the impact of the DART spacecraft. The mathematical models are based on the well-known Kepler problems and have been formulated either in terms of a two-body or a three-body problem. Especially the latter case, provides a series of numerical limitations which do not allow to use it to reliably predict the behavior of the mission. To this aim, an analog/digital circuit which emulates such dynamics has been proposed in [3]. The advantage of such approach is that all the unavoidable imperfections are encompassed in a physical, thus *imperfect* [4], implementation, rather than using a totally ideal approach.

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The behavior of the binary asteroid system, even in its three-body formulation, does not display a significant presence of complexity nor the onset of chaotic oscillations. The unpredictability, therefore, was more linked to the different magnitudes assumed by the variables which lead to numerical errors arising during the integration of the system dynamics, even using complex integration strategies based on symplectic integrators [5].

In this communication, we will focus on the problem of predicting the behavior of a three-body system in which nonlinear oscillations and chaos appear. In this case, numerical errors occurring during its simulation [6] often lead to numerical instability, thus avoiding the possibility to predict correctly the system behavior. Moreover, chaos in the three-body problem [7, 8] occurs for specific initial conditions, with an unstructured basin of attraction. These considerations led to a complete reformulation of the prediction process, taking into account particular machine learning techniques based on quaternions, the so-called hypercomplex neural networks (HNNs) [9–13].

In this communication, we adopt Quaternion-valued MultiLayer Perceptron (QMLP) artificial neural networks, as their formulation maps conceptually the nature of the phenomenon to be modeled. In order to improve learning times and reduce the number of epochs needed for process convergence, we will exploit a recent implementation based on parallel computing of generic MLP-ANNs. The main idea is to exploit the parallel computing capabilities of modern microprocessors in embedded devices to instantiate a set of auxiliary networks devoted to the prediction of the learning algorithm output, thus sensibly reducing the time to get a robust and efficient learning error [14].

The paper is organized as follows. In Sect. 2, details on the chaotic three-body problem are introduced focusing on the peculiar nature of its behavior; mathematical preliminaries related to quaternion algebra are recalled in Sect. 3 together with the Hypercomplex MLP structure

adopted in the paper; numerical results showing the capability of the QMLP of predicting the behavior of the chaotic three-body problem are reported in Sect. 4. Final considerations are drawn in the conclusive section.

2. Chaos in the three-body problem

The three-body problem is one of the most studied nonlinear dynamical system. It represents the motion of three celestial bodies under the sole effects of mutual gravitational effects. Its most general representation is based on the following set of second-order differential equations:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \ddot{X}_1 &= Gm_2 \frac{X_2 - X_1}{r_{12}^3} + Gm_3 \frac{X_3 - X_1}{r_{13}^3} \\
 \ddot{Y}_1 &= Gm_2 \frac{Y_2 - Y_1}{r_{12}^3} + Gm_3 \frac{Y_3 - Y_1}{r_{13}^3} \\
 \ddot{Z}_1 &= Gm_2 \frac{Z_2 - Z_1}{r_{12}^3} + Gm_3 \frac{Z_3 - Z_1}{r_{13}^3} \\
 \ddot{X}_2 &= Gm_1 \frac{X_1 - X_2}{r_{12}^3} + Gm_3 \frac{X_3 - X_2}{r_{23}^3} \\
 \ddot{Y}_2 &= Gm_1 \frac{Y_1 - Y_2}{r_{12}^3} + Gm_3 \frac{Y_3 - Y_2}{r_{23}^3} \\
 \ddot{Z}_2 &= Gm_1 \frac{Z_1 - Z_2}{r_{12}^3} + Gm_3 \frac{Z_3 - Z_2}{r_{23}^3} \\
 \ddot{X}_3 &= Gm_1 \frac{X_1 - X_3}{r_{13}^3} + Gm_2 \frac{X_2 - X_3}{r_{23}^3} \\
 \ddot{Y}_3 &= Gm_1 \frac{Y_1 - Y_3}{r_{13}^3} + Gm_2 \frac{Y_2 - Y_3}{r_{23}^3} \\
 \ddot{Z}_3 &= Gm_1 \frac{Z_1 - Z_3}{r_{13}^3} + Gm_2 \frac{Z_2 - Z_3}{r_{23}^3}
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where (X_1, Y_1, Z_1) , (X_2, Y_2, Z_2) , and (X_3, Y_3, Z_3) are the positions of the three bodies in the inertial space, with mass m_1 , m_2 and m_3 expressed in kg, G is the universal gravitational constant and

$$\begin{aligned}
 r_{12} &= \sqrt{(X_2 - X_1)^2 + (Y_2 - Y_1)^2 + (Z_2 - Z_1)^2} \\
 r_{13} &= \sqrt{(X_3 - X_1)^2 + (Y_3 - Y_1)^2 + (Z_3 - Z_1)^2} \\
 r_{23} &= \sqrt{(X_3 - X_2)^2 + (Y_3 - Y_2)^2 + (Z_3 - Z_2)^2}
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

are the magnitudes of the relative positions of each mass with respect to the others.

The model in Eqs. (1) is a nonlinear system of 18 ordinary differential equations, nine describing the dynamics of the coordinates (X_1, Y_1, Z_1) , (X_2, Y_2, Z_2) , and (X_3, Y_3, Z_3) , i.e. the relative velocity vectors, and nine describing

the dynamics of the relative velocity vectors $(\dot{X}_1, \dot{Y}_1, \dot{Z}_1)$, $(\dot{X}_2, \dot{Y}_2, \dot{Z}_2)$, and $(\dot{X}_3, \dot{Y}_3, \dot{Z}_3)$, i.e. the relative acceleration vectors.

Let us consider the simplified case in which the three masses are identical, i.e. $m_1 = m_2 = m_3 = 1$, and the units are normalized such as the gravitational constant $G = 1$. Moreover, without loss of generality, the positions in the inertial space can be represented with respect to the center of mass of the system, that is equivalent of imposing the constraint that $\sum_{i=1}^3 X_i = \sum_{i=1}^3 Y_i = \sum_{i=1}^3 Z_i = 0$ on the bodies positions and the constraint $\sum_{i=1}^3 \dot{X}_i = \sum_{i=1}^3 \dot{Y}_i = \sum_{i=1}^3 \dot{Z}_i = 0$. Under these considerations, the system in (1) can be recast as the following system of twelve independent differential equations:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \dot{X}_1 &= U_1 \\
 \dot{U}_1 &= \frac{X_2 - X_1}{r_{12}^3} - \frac{X_2 + 2X_1}{r_{13}^3} \\
 \dot{Y}_1 &= V_1 \\
 \dot{V}_1 &= \frac{Y_2 - Y_1}{r_{12}^3} - \frac{Y_2 + 2Y_1}{r_{13}^3} \\
 \dot{Z}_1 &= W_1 \\
 \dot{W}_1 &= \frac{Z_2 - Z_1}{r_{12}^3} - \frac{Z_2 + 2Z_1}{r_{13}^3} \\
 \dot{X}_2 &= U_2 \\
 \dot{U}_2 &= \frac{X_1 - X_2}{r_{12}^3} - \frac{X_1 + 2X_2}{r_{23}^3} \\
 \dot{Y}_2 &= V_2 \\
 \dot{V}_2 &= \frac{Y_1 - Y_2}{r_{12}^3} - \frac{Y_1 + 2Y_2}{r_{23}^3} \\
 \dot{Z}_2 &= W_2 \\
 \dot{W}_2 &= \frac{Z_1 - Z_2}{r_{12}^3} - \frac{Z_1 + 2Z_2}{r_{23}^3}
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
 r_{12} &= \sqrt{(X_2 - X_1)^2 + (Y_2 - Y_1)^2 + (Z_2 - Z_1)^2} \\
 r_{13} &= \sqrt{(X_2 + 2X_1)^2 + (Y_2 + 2Y_1)^2 + (Z_2 + 2Z_1)^2} \\
 r_{23} &= \sqrt{(X_1 + 2X_2)^2 + (Y_1 + 2Y_2)^2 + (Z_1 + 2Z_2)^2}
 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

The chaotic behavior of the proposed model is dictated only by the set of initial conditions, as no free parameters are included. It has been shown that several chaotic attractors coexist, even if the corresponding basins of attraction are irregular. This leads to intrinsic instabilities, due to the high sensitivity of chaotic flows to

initial conditions and digit precision. It should be noted [6, 15] that this behavior is not related to the integration method adopted to determine the trajectory of the system, but it is rather related to the physical limits of predicting the chaotic motion in the three-body problem. While usually for nonlinear systems in which a chaotic dynamics can be observed, the chaotic behavior is sustained, in the three-body problem, the irregular nature of the basins of attraction leads to the observation of a transient chaotic behavior which suddenly diverges.

Let us consider the system in (3) with initial conditions

$$\begin{aligned}
 (X_1(0), Y_1(0), Z_1(0)) &= (0, 0, -1) \\
 (X_2(0), Y_2(0), Z_2(0)) &= (0, 0, 0) \\
 (U_1(0), V_1(0), W_1(0)) &= (0, -1, 0) \\
 (U_2(0), V_2(0), W_2(0)) &= (1, 1, 0)
 \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

The resulting behavior, in a time-window $T = 1000$ s, is shown in Fig. 1. The chaotic trajectory obtained is characterized by a largest Lyapunov exponent $\lambda = 0.1681$ [8]. Increasing the integration time-window T , the trajectory tends to diverge towards infinity. Similarly, slightly perturbing the initial conditions, the trajectory leaves the chaotic attractor and diverges. This has been shown to be not connected to the integration method adopted to obtain the numerical simulation [15], but rather on high intrinsic sensitivity of the three-body problem. Moreover, let us consider the same system (3) with initial conditions

$$\begin{aligned}
 (X_1(0), Y_1(0), Z_1(0)) &= (0, -1, 1) \\
 (X_2(0), Y_2(0), Z_2(0)) &= (0, 0, -2) \\
 (U_1(0), V_1(0), W_1(0)) &= (-1, 0, 0) \\
 (U_2(0), V_2(0), W_2(0)) &= (0, 0, 0)
 \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

The chaotic attractor obtained in this case, shown in Fig. 2, appears less sensitive as it is maintained for a larger time-window, even if for $T > 17000$ s the chaotic flow is again lost.

FIG. 1. Chaotic behavior of system (3) with initial conditions (5).

FIG. 2. Chaotic behavior of system (3) with initial conditions (6).

3. Quaternion Algebra and Hypercomplex Multilayer Perceptrons

It appears evident that, when chaos occurs in the three-body problem, classic approaches for its analysis cannot always be adopted for larger prediction windows. This fact puts a strong limit when designing interplanetary missions similar to DART. Machine learning based solutions, however, can be of help, in particular using innovative solutions based on quaternion-valued networks.

A quaternion \mathbf{q} is defined as a generalized complex number composed of four real

parameters (q_0, q_1, q_2, q_3) and of three imaginary units $(\mathbf{i}, \mathbf{j}, \mathbf{k})$ which represent the basis unit vectors of an orthogonal reference frame:

$$\mathbf{q} = q_0 + q_1\mathbf{i} + q_2\mathbf{j} + q_3\mathbf{k} \tag{7}$$

The role of the imaginary part in quaternion algebra is the same of unit $i = \sqrt{-1}$ in complex algebra. A quaternion can be considered as the sum of a real number q and of a vector q :

$$\mathbf{q} = q_0 + \mathbf{q} \tag{8}$$

In matrix form:

$$\mathbf{q} = [q_0, q_1, q_2, q_3]^T \tag{9}$$

The fundamental quaternion operators are: conjugate: $\mathbf{q}^* = q_0 - q = q_0 - q_1\mathbf{i} - q_2\mathbf{j} - q_3\mathbf{k}$; sum of quaternions $\mathbf{q} + \mathbf{p} = (q_0 + p_0) + (q_1 + p_1)\mathbf{i} + (q_2 + p_2)\mathbf{j} + (q_3 + p_3)\mathbf{k}$; quaternion modulus: $|\mathbf{q}| = \sqrt{q_0^2 + q_1^2 + q_2^2 + q_3^2}$; product of quaternions: $\mathbf{q} \otimes \mathbf{p} = (q_0 + q)\otimes(p_0 + p) = q_0p_0 - q \cdot p + q_0p + p_0q + q \times p$ (where " \cdot " is the scalar product and " \times " represents the vector product). The quaternion product is not commutative, but associative and distributive properties hold. The inverse of a quaternion is defined as $\mathbf{q}^{-1} = \frac{\mathbf{q}^*}{\mathbf{q}^* \otimes \mathbf{q}}$.

A quaternion-valued multilayer perceptron (QMLP) is a multilayer perceptron (MLP) in which input, output, weights and biases are quaternions and activation function is a quaternion-valued one.

Let $n_o, n_h, n_i,$ be the number of output, hidden and input units respectively. We will denote with the superscript O , the quantities relative to the output layer; the superscript H , the quantities relative to the hidden layer; the superscript I , the quantities relative to the input layer.

The weights and the biases are now defined:

- \mathbf{W}_{nm}^{HO} is the weight connecting the m th hidden neuron to the n th output neuron:

$$\mathbf{W}_{nm}^{HO} = \mathbf{w}_{0nm}^{HO} + \mathbf{i}\mathbf{w}_{1nm}^{HO} + \mathbf{j}\mathbf{w}_{2nm}^{HO} + \mathbf{k}\mathbf{w}_{3nm}^{HO} \tag{10}$$

- \mathbf{W}_{nm}^{IH} is the weight connecting the m th input neuron to the n th hidden neuron:

$$\mathbf{W}_{nm}^{IH} = \mathbf{w}_{0nm}^{IH} + \mathbf{i}\mathbf{w}_{1nm}^{IH} + \mathbf{j}\mathbf{w}_{2nm}^{IH} + \mathbf{k}\mathbf{w}_{3nm}^{IH} \quad (11)$$

- Θ_n^H is the n th hidden neuron bias:

$$\Theta_n^H = \theta_{0n}^H + \mathbf{i}\theta_{1n}^H + \mathbf{j}\theta_{2n}^H + \mathbf{k}\theta_{3n}^H \quad (12)$$

The chosen activation function is the quaternion-valued sigmoidal function:

$$\mathbf{X}_n = \boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{S}_n) = \boldsymbol{\sigma}(S_{0n}) + \mathbf{i}\boldsymbol{\sigma}(S_{1n}) + \mathbf{j}\boldsymbol{\sigma}(S_{2n}) + \mathbf{k}\boldsymbol{\sigma}(S_{3n}) \quad (13)$$

where $\sigma(x) = \frac{1}{1+e^{-x}}$ that is the usual sigmoidal real valued activation function. The activation function derivative is:

$$\dot{\boldsymbol{\sigma}}(\cdot) = \dot{\sigma}(\cdot) + \mathbf{i}\dot{\sigma}(\cdot) + \mathbf{j}\dot{\sigma}(\cdot) + \mathbf{k}\dot{\sigma}(\cdot) \quad (14)$$

where $\dot{\sigma}(\cdot) = \sigma(\cdot)[1 - \sigma(\cdot)]$

The feed-forward phase is shown in the following:

- the hidden unit activation value is computed in the following way:

$$\mathbf{S}_n^H = \sum_{m=1}^{n_i} (\mathbf{W}_{nm}^{IH} \otimes \mathbf{I}_m) + \Theta_n^H \quad (15)$$

- the hidden unit output value will be:

$$\mathbf{X}_n^H = \boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{S}_n^H) = \boldsymbol{\sigma}(S_{0n}^H) + \mathbf{i}\boldsymbol{\sigma}(S_{1n}^H) + \mathbf{j}\boldsymbol{\sigma}(S_{2n}^H) + \mathbf{k}\boldsymbol{\sigma}(S_{3n}^H) \quad (16)$$

- the output unit activation value is computed in the following way:

$$\mathbf{S}_n^O = \sum_{m=1}^{n_h} (\mathbf{W}_{nm}^{HO} \otimes \mathbf{X}_m^H) + \Theta_n^O \quad (17)$$

- the n th output unit value will be:

$$\mathbf{Y}_n = \mathbf{X}_n^O = \boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{S}_n^O) = \boldsymbol{\sigma}(S_{0n}^O) + \mathbf{i}\boldsymbol{\sigma}(S_{1n}^O) + \mathbf{j}\boldsymbol{\sigma}(S_{2n}^O) + \mathbf{k}\boldsymbol{\sigma}(S_{3n}^O) \quad (18)$$

The error function between the actual output of the network $\mathbf{Y}_n = Y_{0n} + \mathbf{i}Y_{1n} + \mathbf{j}Y_{2n} + \mathbf{k}Y_{3n}$ and the desired n th target $\mathbf{t}_n = t_{0n} + \mathbf{i}t_{1n} + \mathbf{j}t_{2n} + \mathbf{k}t_{3n}$ is defined as:

$$E = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{n=1}^{n_0} [(t_{0n} - Y_{0n})^2 + (t_{1n} - Y_{1n})^2 + (t_{2n} - Y_{2n})^2 + (t_{3n} - Y_{3n})^2] \quad (19)$$

The backpropagation algorithm for QMLPs is dual to the one adopted for classic MLPs. First of all the output error is calculated:

$$\mathbf{e}_n^O = t_n - \mathbf{X}_n^O \quad (20)$$

where t_n is the target relative to the n pattern.

Then the propagation of the error from output layer to hidden one δ_h^{OH} is computed:

$$\delta_h^{OH} = e_{0n}^{OH} \dot{\sigma}(S_{0n}^O) + \mathbf{i}e_{1n}^{OH} \dot{\sigma}(S_{1n}^O) + \mathbf{j}e_{2n}^{OH} \dot{\sigma}(S_{2n}^O) + \mathbf{k}e_{3n}^{OH} \dot{\sigma}(S_{3n}^O) \quad (21)$$

where $h = 0, \dots, N_O$ is the number of the neuron considered in the output layer.

The correction of the weights and biases of the hidden layer neurons is computed with the following formula:

$$\Delta \mathbf{W}_{hn}^{HO} = \eta \delta_n^H \otimes (\mathbf{X}_h^H)^* \quad (22)$$

$$\Delta \Theta_n^H = \epsilon \delta_n^H \quad (23)$$

We get the error relative to the hidden layer from:

$$\mathbf{e}_n^H = \sum_{h=1}^{N_O} (\mathbf{W}_{hn}^{HO})^* \otimes \delta_h^{OH} \quad (24)$$

and then we can compute δ_h^{HI} as done in the hidden layer case:

$$\delta_h^{HI} = e_{0n}^{OH} \dot{\sigma}(S_{0n}^H) + \mathbf{i}e_{1n}^{OH} \dot{\sigma}(S_{1n}^H) + \mathbf{j}e_{2n}^{OH} \dot{\sigma}(S_{2n}^H) + \mathbf{k}e_{3n}^{OH} \dot{\sigma}(S_{3n}^H) \quad (25)$$

One of the primary objectives in the field of neural networks research is to achieve optimal predictive performance with the least possible time investment. In previous works such as [16] and [14], a strategy has been developed to improve convergence time through parallelization of the learning phase, by utilizing auxiliary networks to predict weight trends during the learning phase, the aim is to reduce the required number of epochs.

Although increasing the learning rate η can expedite the learning phase, it can lead to oscillation of the error gradient. To mitigate this issue, the following equation can be employed:

$$\Delta_p \mathbf{W}_{ij}(k) = \eta \delta_{pj}(k) \mathbf{o}_{pi}(k) + \rho \Delta_p \mathbf{W}_{ij}(k-1) \quad (26)$$

where ρ represents the momentum. From this equation a dynamical system of the network weights changes could be built. Then we can exploit the capability in interpolating of ANNs in order to predict the weight values at a given iteration.

We will get a time series as:

$$\{\mathbf{W}_{ij}(k)\} \text{ with } k_{min} < k < k_{max} \quad (27)$$

The aim of the auxiliary networks is to predict the right value of the weight at a given discrete time k^* . The discrete time samples serve as inputs, while the outputs consist of the four coefficients of the quaternionic weight. To ensure faster learning than the main network, it is crucial

for the auxiliary networks to have a small number of neurons.

Once the main network surpasses the initial learning phase, the weights of the original network undergo gradual and slow changes over time. Furthermore, certain weights experience lesser changes compared to others. As a result, it can be assumed that the corresponding weight has reached the optimal value and they don't need to be considered by auxiliary networks. Once the weights are predicted, they are transferred to the main network and substituted into the existing weight matrix. Subsequently, the error is computed based on these updated weights. The acceptance of the new weight matrix is contingent upon satisfying the following condition:

$$E(\mathbf{W}_{pred}) < E(\mathbf{W}_{prec}) \quad (28)$$

where $E(\mathbf{W}_{pred})$ represents the error associated to the predicted weight matrix and $E(\mathbf{W}_{prec})$ is the error associated with the weight matrix before the substitution.

4. Numerical results

In this Section, the prediction capabilities of properly trained QMLPs are tested by considering two case studies. At first, we will address the prediction of the behavior of system in Eqs. (3), with the set of initial conditions (5), beyond the time-window allowed by numerical simulations. As a second case study, we will refer to the nonlinear motion of Mercury around the Sun, taking the Earth as reference.

4.1. Predicting chaos in the three-body problem

Let us consider the chaotic attractor in Fig. 1. We use the first 1380 over 1500 samples of the simulation for the learning of the proposed network and the following 120 for the evaluation of the prediction of the network. In particular, we

selected as training data, the three positions of the first body and the relative velocity along the X direction.

The QMLP has three hidden layers with 5–10–5, with learning rate 0.01, momentum 0.5 and using the proposed parallel learning strategy.

By considering that k is the index of the considered sample, the networks are trained to map the inputs that are spacial coordinates and the velocity along the X direction of five consecutive points $[p_{k-5}, p_{k-2}, \dots, p_{k-1}]$ on the trajectory and the outputs are the three spacial coordinates and the velocity of the point p_k .

The evaluation process begins by using the samples indexed from $k - 5$ to $k - 1$ as initial conditions. The QMLP is then tasked with predicting the sample indexed as k and feeding this predicted point as input for the subsequent prediction.

To evaluate the prediction performance of the network, an n -step prediction is performed. At first the one-step-ahead prediction capabilities are tested, i.e. $n = 1$. Results are shown in Figs. 3 and 4 and allow to determine the generally high performance of the trained QMLP.

FIG. 3. QMLP one-step-ahead prediction in comparison with the original trajectory.

A larger prediction window, i.e. $n = 15$, is considered in Figs. 5 and 6. Despite the slight inaccuracy of the prediction, the network output follows with a good agreement the original trajectory, without diverging to infinity.

FIG. 4. Mean square error of the QMLP one-step-ahead prediction for each dataset.

FIG. 5. QMLP n -step-ahead prediction in comparison with the original trajectory.

FIG. 6. Mean square error of the QMLP n -step-ahead prediction for each dataset.

The prediction window can be further increased maintaining a sufficient level of accuracy. The trained network is generally capable to follow the chaotic trajectory, even beyond the observation window of numerical integrations.

4.2. Mercury motion in a three-body environment

The coordinates of Mercury in the inertial space defined by the Earth have been taken from the "SPICE" information system, offered by the Navigation and Ancillary Information Facility (NAIF). Coordinates are used to generate the patterns for the training and evaluation of the performance of the quaternion-valued network.

In our case, it was possible to extract the data regarding the trajectory of Mercury, by using the Earth as the observer (more specifically, we discuss the barycenter of the two planet system) in a three-dimensional reference frame.

FIG. 7. Two-years trajectory of Mercury around the Sun with respect to the Earth.

The trajectory of Mercury barycenter between the 1st of January 2001 and the 1st of January 2003 is reported in Fig. 7. Then, the resulting curve has been sampled into 1500 points that in terms of sampling period is about 11 hours and 40 minutes.

The results achieved by the considered

QMLP are shown in Fig. 8, that represents 15-step prediction of the network versus the original curve, and in Fig. 9, that represents the point-to-point mean square error for each coordinate, after that the network have been trained for 15000 epochs.

FIG. 8. Comparison between the original trajectory and that predicted by the trained QMLP.

FIG. 9. Point-to-point mean square error for each coordinate.

The performances of the QMLP are good in terms of error of the prediction versus the original curve. This improvement in terms of learning cycles, together with the fewer number of parameter adopted for the QMLP architecture, gives an idea of the learning power of this tool.

Emphasizing the significance of accuracy, it is crucial to note that further enhancements can

be achieved by increasing the number of epochs during the learning phase, while utilizing a lower learning rate and incorporating a larger number of samples. In our study, we conducted our analysis using a limited number of cycles and samples, considering the complexity of the approximation problem at hand. However, it is worth mentioning that a more comprehensive exploration of these parameters could lead to improved results and a more robust solution.

5. Conclusions

The DART mission has been spectacularly effective notwithstanding the high number of possible inaccuracies occurring during the design of the mission itself [17] since the effective momentum that the DART spacecraft transferred to Dimorphos was not completely predictable as non-ideality sources may have had a strong impact on the mission outcome.

The nonlinear systems theory provides a potentially fundamental added value to the design of effective interplanetary missions. However, when considering complex gravitational interplays, intrinsically unpredictable behaviors can occur, thus diminishing drastically the possibility of a positive outcome. We have shown that when chaos occurs in the three-body problem, not only numerical integration

errors may arise, but also digit precision plays a crucial role in predicting the behavior. To face this problem, we proposed a strategy based on hypercomplex neural network which is able to allow an improved prediction horizon even in presence of limited digit precision.

The strategy outlined in this paper can be further improved by considering more complex learning methods, parallelizing the Levenberg-Marquadt method [18] with the aim of further extending the prediction accuracy, even in larger time-windows.

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